

Fig. 2

the quinoline insoluble fraction of pitch 14 revealing a larger number of spins than the corresponding fraction from pitch 16. The similarity in infra-red and e.s.r. behaviour is carried one step further by the fact that the quinoline insoluble fraction of pitch 5 (a lignite pitch) has an abnormally low spin concentration as compared to the corresponding fractions from the other two pitches. In the infra-red study also, the quinoline insoluble fraction of pitch 5 showed an abnormally low background absorption at 2μ .

A similar demarcation is possible when the line widths are compared of the unfiltered pitches and their quinoline soluble and insoluble fractions, the line widths being higher in the case of the quinoline soluble fractions, and smaller with the quinoline insoluble fractions than with the corresponding unfiltered pitches. The only differences is that whereas with the unfiltered pitches, the spin concentration increased with increase in the quinoline insoluble content, no such relationship is noticeable with the line width. Pitch 5, as also its quinoline insoluble fraction, forms an exception even here.

The g -values, however, show no trend.

The close similarity between the electron spin resonance and the infra-red behaviour of the pitches throws light on the nature of the free radical species in pitches. Walker and Baumbach¹ have suggested previously that background absorption at 2μ originates from the electrons in pitches. Following Ingram⁴, these mobile electrons stabilised by aromatic ring clusters seem to be responsible for the free radical behaviour of the pitches. The narrowing of line-width at high free radical concentration, as also the oxygen effect mentioned above, is in line with the above explanation.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Dr. Weiler of the Allied Chemical Corporation for the separation of the pitches, and to Dr. P. L. Walker, Jr. for a Senior Research

Associateship (at the Department of Materials Science, Penn State University), which made the work possible.

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Studies on Hydroxofluoromolybdates (V) of the Type $[\text{Mo}(\text{OH})\text{F}_6]^{2-}$

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Manuscript received 23 December 1972; accepted 18 July 1973

STUDIES on the fluoro or oxofluoromolybdates (V) are very scanty. Three such series of anionic complexes, viz., $[\text{MoF}_8]^{3-}$, $[\text{MoF}_6]^-$ and $[\text{MoOF}_5]^{2-}$ have been reported¹. These compounds have been mostly prepared from nonaqueous medium. We are presenting here the isolation of salts of a new series of hydroxofluoromolybdates (V), viz., $M_2[\text{Mo}(\text{OH})\text{F}_6]$ (where $M = \text{K}, \text{Rb}, \text{Cs}, \text{Tl}, \frac{1}{2}\text{N}_2\text{H}_6$ and $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}$) from aqueous solution. The salts have been characterised by elemental analysis, determination of oxidation number of molybdenum, magnetic susceptibility measurement and i.r. spectral studies.

Experimental and Discussion

The parent compound of this series, $\text{N}_2\text{H}_6[\text{Mo}(\text{OH})\text{F}_6]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained by reducing a solution of MoO_3 in 40% HF at water bath temperature with hydrazine (80%) neutralised with the same acid.

NOTES

The green solution deposited fine crystals on concentration over water bath or in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 and NaOH. The potassium, rubidium, caesium and thallium(I) salts were obtained by mixing concentrated solutions of the alkali fluorides or of thallose nitrate with a concentrated solution of the hydrazinium(II) salt in 20% HF medium. All these are crystalline and green in colour, except the thallium(I) salt which is pale green. Analysis of the filter pressed hydrazinium(II) salt dried over H_2SO_4 and NaOH corresponded to the monohydrate $N_2H_6[Mo(OH)F_6].H_2O$, while the other salts similarly dried analysed as the anhydrous compounds, *viz.*, $M_2M[Mo(OH)F_6]$.

The methods of analysis of molybdenum, fluorine and nitrogen were the same as described before². The alkali metals were estimated gravimetrically as their sulphates after separation of molybdenum as sulphide. The analytical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

The salts are stable when dry, but the moist samples turn blue. They dissolve in water to give green solutions which gradually change to light orange. They are soluble in dilute HF. The hydrazinium(II) and the potassium salts could be recrystallised from 20% HF. The hydrazinium(II) salt turns blue-green on heating at 110° with the liberation of hydrogen fluoride while the potassium salt is stable at this temperature.

The formulation of the complexes is based on complete elemental analysis, determination of the oxidation state of molybdenum, magnetic moment values and i.r. spectral studies. The oxidation number of molybdenum in the potassium, rubidium and caesium salts determined by oxidation with hot acid dichromate was about +5. Since hydrazine is not quantitatively oxidised by dichromate in dilute sulphuric acid medium³, a rough estimate of the oxidation state of molybdenum in the hydrazine salt was made by subtracting the amount of dichromate consumed

by the hydrazine content determined in a separate experiment by oxidising $N_2H_6F_2$ under similar conditions, from the total amount of the dichromate consumed by the sample. The valency of molybdenum thus came around 5. The effective magnetic moments of all the salts (Table 1) fall within the range 1.56 to 1.82 BM at 30°. The magnetic susceptibility of a sample of the potassium salt heated to 110° remains unchanged indicating that no dimerisation of the hydroxo complex takes place.

The i.r. spectra of the potassium, rubidium and caesium salts give the characteristic $\nu(O-H)$ band at 3250–3550 cm^{-1} , while $\delta(H-O-H)$ band was absent. The hydrazinium salt gave $\delta(H-O-H)$ band at 1630 cm^{-1} , and also $\nu(O-H)$ band, the latter having been overlapped with the $\nu(N-H)$ band. Another important feature of the spectra of all these salts is the presence of a very strong and intense band at 980–990 cm^{-1} which falls within the diagnostic region of $Mo=O$ vibration. However, an oxo-grouping is difficult to be accommodated in the formulae of the hexafluoro complexes on the basis of the elemental analysis of the quinquevalent molybdenum compounds. The alternative formulation of the salts as $M_2^+H[MoOF_6]$ or $M_2^+[MoOF_5].HF$ where $M = K, Rb, Cs, Tl$ and $\frac{1}{2}N_2H_6$ is not favoured since the spectra of the potassium, rubidium and caesium salts exhibit the characteristic $\nu(O-H)$ band even in the absence of $\delta(H-O-H)$ band. Thus we assign the 980–990 cm^{-1} band in the complexes arising due to the deformation mode of $Mo-O-H$ group. This assignment is consistent with the evidence for such a band in the region 920–1000 cm^{-1} in certain ruthenium complexes⁴, at 1050–1090 cm^{-1} in some Os(V) complexes⁵, at 960–1010 cm^{-1} for Re(V) complexes⁶ and at 965 cm^{-1} in certain Mo(IV) complexes⁷. The spectral features of the hydrazinium salt resemble those of $N_2H_6^{++}$ salts rather than $N_2H_5^+$ salt⁸. The band positions in the i.r. spectra of all the salts were identical when the spectra are recorded either in potassium bromide pellet or in nujol mull.

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	Mo	% calc. F	Alkali metal or N	Mo	% found F	Alkali metal or N	μ_{eff} , B.M.
1. $N_2H_6[Mo(OH)F_6].H_2O$	Green	<u>34.39</u>	40.86	10.03	<u>33.3</u>	40.4	10.3	1.56
2. $K_2[Mo(OH)F_6]$	Green	31.44	37.35	25.75	31.8	37.8	26.6	1.71
3. $Rb_2[Mo(OH)F_6]$	Green	24.11	28.65	42.96	23.9	28.5	44.1	1.82
4. $Cs_2[Mo(OH)F_6]$	Green	<u>19.47</u>	23.13	53.94	<u>18.7</u>	22.8	54.4	1.68
5. $Tl_2[Mo(OH)F_6]$	Pale green	15.09	17.93	64.30	15.3	17.6	63.3	1.76
6. $(C_{10}H_{10}N)_2[Mo(OH)F_6]$	Green	18.62	22.11	5.43	18.7	21.6	5.6	1.58

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Chemical Examination of *Lantana camara* Linn.

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Manuscript received 4 January 1973; accepted 7 July 1973

LANTANA CAMARA Linn (N.O. Verbenaceae) causes severe photosensitisation during fruiting and flowering stages¹ and icterus in sheep. The leaves of the plant were extensively examined and isolated the triterpenes lantadene A, lantadene B^{2,3,4}, lantalic acid, lactic acid and 3-Keto ursolic acid⁵⁻⁸ and an unidentified ketosteroid lancamarone⁹.

In the present investigation the roots of the plant were examined. The root powder was extracted with hot EtOH and the extract on removal of the solvent gave a dark greenish brown residue (3%). The residue was fractionated into Et₂O (2%) and H₂O (1%) solubles. (The aqueous extract gave yellow colour with alkali and blue colour with acid). The Et₂O extract was fractionated into neutral (0.1% waxes) and acidic (1.9%) fractions by extraction with 5% NaOH. TLC on silica gel G indicated that the acid is a mixture of three or four compounds. One was separated and purified by fractional crystallisation from EtOH and chromatography over silica gel and identified as oleanolic acid (1.5%) C, 98.72; H, 10.81. C₃₀H₄₈O₃ requires C, 98.95 and H, 10.53%. (C, 1.2 in CHCl₃): m.p. 290°-92°: [α]_D+80°, I.R. 1665 cm⁻¹, 825 cm⁻¹: NMR spectra multiplet centered at 4.7τ (IH) for trisubstituted double bond: Prominent MS: right-half ratio Diels-Alder fragment m/e 248, m/e 233 (248-CH₃) and m/e 189 (233-CO₂): comparison of the acetate with authentic oleanolic acid acetate (m.m.p. and IR)].

The separation of the other compounds could not be effected as their R values are very close. The efforts for the separation and characterisation of the other triterpenes are in progress.

Acknowledgement

We thank Prof. L. Ramachandra Row, Head of the Chemistry Department, Andhra University, Waltair, for a sample of oleanolic acid acetate, Prof. N. V. Subba Rao, Head of the Chemistry Department, Osmania University, Hyderabad, for spectral data and the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Synthesis of 3,5-Dimethyl-1-naphthol*

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THE preparation of 3,5-dimethyl-1-naphthol from *o*-xylene after suitable modification of the sequence of reactions shown in Fig. 1 and reported earlier by Royals and Green² for the synthesis of 3,5-dimethyl-1-tetralone is described.

Experimental

*Diethyl (o-xyllyl) malonate*¹ (II): α -Bromo-*o*-xylene³ (I) (23.0 g; 0.12 M), b.p. 102°/15 mm; n_D^{30} 1.5746, obtained from *o*-xylene using N-bromosuccinimide as the brominating agent³ was treated with sodium

* Communication No. 1652, National Chemical Laboratory, Poona 8, India.